

Synthesis, characterization and evaluation of *in vitro* antimicrobial activity of carbonyl derivatives of sulphonamide compounds

Keisham Surjit Singh^{a*}, Sanasam Sachika Devi^a, Manojit Roy^a and W. Radhapiyari Devi^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology Agartala, Jirania-799 055, Tripura West, India
E-mail : surjitkeisham@yahoo.co.in, singh1971@gmail.com

^bInstitute of Bioresources and Sustainable Development, IBSD, Takyelpat, Imphal-795 001, Manipur, India

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Abstract : Sulphonamide compounds (1-4) were synthesized by simple condensation of sulphanilamide with carbonyl derivatives. The compounds were characterized by elemental analysis, IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy. All the carbonyl derivatives form Schiff base compounds (2-4) with sulphanilamide while with acetylacetone; the Schiff base compound formed undergoes *keto-enol* tautomer and then crystallized as 4-(4-oxopent-2-en-2-ylamino)benzene sulfonamide compound (1) in which azomethine nitrogen atom is protonated. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy data indicates the formation of the compounds and reveals the protonation of azomethine nitrogen atom in compound 1 which has also been confirmed by X-ray crystal structure. All the compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities against different microbes. Compound 1 and 2 were found to be effective antifungal agents against *C. albicans* while 3 and 4 shown antibacterial activities against *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella paratyphi*. The minimum inhibition concentration of all the compounds were also determined and compared with standard drugs.

Keywords : Sulphonamides, X-ray crystallography, antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Introduction

Sulphonamide derivative drugs could act selectively and be used as preventive and therapeutic agents against various diseases¹. Sulphonamides family are efficient against pathogenic germs and were found to be useful in many pharmaceutical applications²⁻⁵. Several spectrophotometric methods were reported by many workers for determining sulphonamides in pharmaceutical preparation³⁻⁵. Apart from pharmaceutical applications, sulphonamides can also be used as proton-conducting materials for applications in solid state electrochemical devices like smart windows and sensors⁶. In addition to this, sulphonamide Schiff base compounds possessing potential antibacterial and antifungal can be prepared in good yields and high purity through the straightforward condensation between an amine and a carbonyl compounds². In this context, sulphonamide Schiff base and their metal complexes have been prepared and investigated for physiologically relevant carbonic anhydrase⁷. The antibacterial and antifungal activities of sulphonamides and their metal complexes against various microbes were

also studied and reported to be effective⁸⁻¹⁰. Two compounds reported here has been reported earlier by some workers¹¹⁻¹³. However, the compounds were not systematically characterized. Therefore, in this present work, we have synthesized and characterized a series of Schiff base sulphonamide derivatives by simple condensation of sulphanilamide with acetyl acetone, veratraldehyde, salicylaldehyde and 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone with high purity and better yield. All these carbonyl compounds form Schiff base compounds with sulphanilamide (compound 2-4) while with acetyl acetone, it forms compound 1 which was found to be crystallized as protonated azomethine acetyl acetone alkenyl sulphonamide that has also been confirmed by X-ray crystal structure analysis. All these compounds were fully characterized by elemental analysis, IR and NMR spectroscopy, and were investigated for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against various microorganisms. The minimum inhibitory concentration of all the compounds were determined and compared with standard drugs, Amphotericin-B for antifungal and Ciprofloxacin for antibacterial activities.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The carbonyl derivatives of sulphonamides were obtained by condensation reaction of sulphanilamide with acetyl acetone, veratraldehyde, salicylaldehyde and 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone. All the carbonyl compounds form Schiff base compounds with sulphanilamide while with acetylacetone, it is believed to form initially Schiff base compound which undergoes *keto-enol* tautomerism to give intermediate *enol* compound (Scheme 1A and 1B). The hydrogen atom from the hydroxyl group of the *enol* compound was then shifted to nitrogen atom of azomethine group resulting with the protonation of nitrogen atom and thereby forming the alkenyl *keto*-sulphonamide derivative (Scheme 1C). The general reactions for the preparation of compounds **1** to **4** from sulphanilamide and carbonyl derivatives are given in Scheme 2.

Spectroscopy :

The IR spectra of compound **1** shows bands at 1625 cm^{-1} and 1595 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to C=O and C=N groups. All other sulphonamide compounds show the absence of band at $1698\text{--}1745\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of carbonyl compounds, instead a new prominent band at around $1618\text{--}1595\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to azomethine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ linkage appeared in all the compounds indicating the condensation between carbonyl moiety and that of amino group of sulphanilamide^{14,15}. The bands that appear near 3375 and 3250 cm^{-1} in all the compounds are due to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{NH}_2)$ while the bands at 1300 cm^{-1} and 1025 cm^{-1} may be assigned to symmetric and asymmetric vibration of sulphone group $\nu(\text{O}=\text{S}=\text{O})$ ^{2,9,16}. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of the compounds were recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$

and data are given in Experimental section. The NMR spectroscopy data indicates the formation of the compounds and reveals the protonation of azomethine nitrogen atom in compound **1** which was also confirmed by X-ray crystallography. The ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **1** shows singlet peak at δ 12.57, 2.1 and 2.08 ppm which are assigned to -NH-, -COCH₃ and -CH₃ protons respectively while the multiplet peaks around 6.5–7.5 ppm are due to aromatic protons^{17,18}. The chemical shift value at δ 6.9 and 5.8 ppm are assigned to the SO₂NH₂ protons and $>\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{H})$ - protons^{12,18}. The proton NMR spectra of all other compounds **2–4** show multiplet peaks around δ 6.9–7.4 and 6.5–7.8 ppm due to SO₂NH₂ protons and aromatic protons^{12,19,20}. Compound **3** and **4** shows a singlet peaks at around δ 12.66 which are due to the phenolic OH protons (2-OH) present in the phenyl ring. The proton NMR spectrum of compound **4** also shows a singlet peaks at δ 9.02 ppm which may be assigned to the phenolic OH proton (4-OH) present in the phenyl ring while singlet peak δ 3.37 is due to CH₃-C=N protons. The ^1H NMR integration values and ^{13}C NMR signals of the compounds were fully consistent with the formulation of the products.

Crystallography :

Compound **1** suitable for crystal structure determination was obtained from methanol by slow evaporation. The crystal structure and packing diagram for the compound are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 while crystallography data is given in Table 1. The compound crystallized as orthorhombic with *Pbca* space group. The crystal structure of the compound confirms the protonation of azomethine nitrogen atom and reveals that the compound was resulted via the formation of intermediate *enol* com-

Scheme 1. Numbering of carbon skeleton and different possible structures of compound **1**.

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Scheme 2. Reaction of sulphanilamide with various carbonyl derivatives.

compound (Scheme 1) and subsequent protonation of N-atom followed by shifting of double bond between the adjacent neighboring carbon atoms. The crystal packing structure of the compound also confirms the presence of intermolecular H-bonds between the adjacent neighboring molecules. The intra-molecular hydrogen bond found in this protonated imine is within the range of the reported azoimino benzoic acids where N-H atom forms intra-molecular hydrogen bond with adjacent deprotonated phe-

nolic hydroxyl oxygen atom²¹.

Antibacterial and antifungal activity :

Antifungal and antibacterial activity of the sulphonamide compounds **1-4** were studied against *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, *C. albicans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella paratyphi* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The results of the antimicrobial activities of the compounds were compared with standard drugs, Amphotericin-B for antifungal and Ciprofloxacin for antibacterial activities and

Fig. 1. Molecular structure compound **1** showing atom labeling scheme (50% probability ellipsoids).

Fig. 2. Packing diagram of compound **1** showing H-bonds and weak interactions.

the results are given in Table 2. From the table, it is clear that compound **1** and **2** exhibited antifungal activities against *C. albicans* while **3** has shown antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and **4** was found to be antibacterial agents against *Salmonella paratyphi*. All these compounds were found to be inactive against *A. flavus*, *A. niger* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of the compounds were also determined against the fungal and bacteria species and compared with the standard drugs in Table 3. The MICs of the compounds were found to be in the range of 3000 and $> 3000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The observed antibacterial and antifungal results are comparable with other reported compounds^{18,22,23}. However, this series of compounds are less effective than the standard drugs.

Experimental

Material and methods :

Elemental analyses were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer

2400 series II elemental analyzer. IR spectra in the range of $4000\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were obtained on Shimadzu FT-IR-8400S model spectrophotometer using KBr discs. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AMX 300 spectrophotometer and measured at 300.13 and 75.46 MHz respectively. ^1H and ^{13}C chemical shifts were referred to Me_4Si set at 0.00 ppm. Reactions were monitored by TLC on silica gel 60 F254 (0.25 mm). All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and used without further purifications and solvents were dried following standard procedures.

Synthesis of 4-(4-oxopentan-2-ylideneamino)benzenesulfonamide (**1**) :

Sulphanilamide (14.8 mmol, 2.5456 g) was dissolved in 20 mL anhydrous methanol by stirring then acetylacetone (14.8 mmol, 1.481 g) in 5 mL anhydrous methanol was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was continued stirring at room temperature for 8 h. The

Table 1. Crystallographic data and structural refinement parameters for compound **1**

Empirical formula	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S
Formula weight	254.30
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073
Crystal system	Orthorhombic
Space group	<i>Pbca</i>
<i>a</i> (Å)	10.3053(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	9.9789(4)
<i>c</i> (Å)	23.3243(8)
α (°)	90
β (°)	90
γ (°)	90
Volume (Å ³)	2398.57(14)
Z (Å ³)	8
Density (mg/m ³)	1.408
Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	0.268
Crystal size (mm)	0.35 × 0.30 × 0.30
Max. and min. transmission	0.9563 and 0.9023
Reflections collected	20540
Independent reflections (<i>R</i> _{int})	0.0296
<i>R</i> (<i>F</i>) [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	0.0873
2θ _{max} (°)	25
w <i>R</i> (<i>F</i> ²) (all data)	0.09
GOF (<i>F</i> ²)	1.042
Max, min Δρ (e Å ⁻³)	0.274 and -0.300

completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC using ethyl acetate-hexane solvent system as eluent. The resulting reaction mixture was then concentrated and evaporated on a water bath and kept in refrigerator. The light yellow solid product was obtained which was filtered and washed with petroleum ether then dried in vacuum. The dried compound was recrystallized from methanol which

afforded light yellow crystalline compound. Yield : 80%; m.p. : 96–100 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₄N₂O₃S : C, 51.95; H, 5.55; N, 11.02; S, 12.60. Found : C, 51.90; H, 5.60; N, 11.10; S, 12.15%; FT-IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3329 (N-H)_{asym}, 3240 (N-H)_{sym}, 2991 (Ar C-H)_{str}, 1626 (CO), 1595 (C=N), 1330 (S=O)_{asym}, 1195 (S=O)_{sym}; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 12.57 (1H, s, NH), 6.9 (2H, d, SO₂NH₂), 6.5–7.7 (4H, m, Ar-H), 5.8 (1H, s, C(H)=C), 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃-CO), 2.08 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 196.5 (C=O), 29.6 (CH₃-CO), 20.2 (CH₃), other signals : 158.9, 152.1, 142.1, 140.1, 130.5, 127.8, 123.1, 112.9, 99.7.

Synthesis of 4-(3,4-dimethoxybenzylidene)benzene-sulfonamide (2) :

The compound (**2**) was prepared by refluxing veratraldehyde (14.1 mmol, 2.36 g) and sulphanilamide (14.1 mmol, 2.41 g) in 30 mL methanol for 6 h. The reaction mixture was filtered and the product was washed with diethyl ether then recrystallized from methanol to give yellow crystalline compound. Yield : 85%; m.p. : 198–203 °C; 187–89 °C for earlier report¹²; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₆N₂O₄S : C, 56.24; H, 5.03; N, 8.74; S, 10.02. Found : C, 56.20; H, 5.0; N, 8.67; S, 10.25%; FT-IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3346 (N-H)_{asym}, 3001 (Ar C-H)_{str}, 1618 (C=N), 1338 (S=O)_{asym}, 1159 (S=O)_{sym}; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 8.54 (1H, s, C(H)=N), 7.11–7.88 (7H, m, Ar-H), 7.39 (2H, d, SO₂NH₂), 3.84 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.86 (3H, s, OCH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 162.6 (C=N), 55.9 (OCH₃), 56.9 (OCH₃), other signals : 141.2, 127.9, 127.4, 126.6, 125.2, 121.7, 112.9, 111.8, 109.9. Other compounds **3** and **4** were prepared

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of sulphonamide compounds^a (zone of inhibition in mm)

Compd.	Fungi			Bacteria		
	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. paratyphi</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
1	–	–	10	–	–	–
2	–	–	10	–	–	–
3	–	–	–	12	–	–
4	–	–	–	–	12	–
Amphotericin-B	32	38	40	–	–	–
Ciprofloxacin	–	–	–	36	34	34

^a*In vitro* agar well-diffusion method, concentrations : 3 mg mL⁻¹ in DMSO, reference drugs, Amphotericin-B for antifungal test and Ciprofloxacin for antibacterial test : 16 µg mL⁻¹ in DMSO, dash (–) indicated inactivity.

Table 3. Minimum inhibition concentration (MIC) for antimicrobial activities of sulphonamide compounds^a

Compd.	MIC for tested fungi and bacteria (Concentration in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)					
	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. paratyphi</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
1	3000	3000	3000	> 3000	> 3000	> 3000
2	3000	3000	3000	> 3000	> 3000	> 3000
3	> 3000	> 3000	> 3000	3000	3000	3000
4	> 3000	> 3000	> 3000	3000	3000	3000
Amphotericin-B	0.5	0.5	> 0.5			
Ciprofloxacin				0.5	0.5	0.5

^aIn *vitro* agar well-diffusion method, concentrations : $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in DMSO, reference drugs, Amphotericin-B for antifungal test and Ciprofloxacin for antibacterial test : $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in DMSO.

by reacting sulphanilamide with appropriate carbonyl derivatives following the analogous procedures.

Synthesis of 4-(2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)benzenesulfonamide (3) :

Yield : 90%; m.p. : 212–213 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 56.51; H, 4.38; N, 10.14; S, 11.61. Found : C, 56.00; H, 4.25; N, 10.29, S, 11.35%; FT-IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3324 (N-H)_{asym}, 3244 (N-H)_{sym}, 3064 (Ar C-H)_{str}, 1618 (C=N), 1315 (S=O)_{asym}, 1165 (S=O)_{sym}; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 12.66 (1H, s, OH), 9.02 (1H, s, C(H)=N), 7.03 (2H, m, SO₂NH₂), 7.1–7.94 (8H, m, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 171.9 (C-OH), 164.9 (C=N), other signals : 133.8, 132.4, 127.0, 121.7, 119.3, 116.6, 112.4.

Synthesis of 4-(1-(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)ethylideneamino)benzenesulfonamide (4) :

Yield : 75%; m.p. : 130–133 °C; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$: C, 54.89; H, 4.61; N, 9.14; S, 10.45. Found : C, 54.80; H, 4.65; N, 9.22; S, 10.21%; FT-IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3477 (O-H)_{str}, 3375 (N-H)_{asym}, 3267 (N-H)_{sym}, 3068 (Ar C-H)_{str}, 1595 (C=N), 1315 (S=O)_{asym}, 1147 (S=O)_{sym}; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 12.66 (1H, s, OH(*ortho*)), 10.66 (1H, s, OH(*para*)), 6.6–7.5 (7H, m, ArH), 6.93 (2H, s, SO₂NH₂), 3.41 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 19.7 (CH₃), 162.5 (C-OH), 162.2 (C-OH), 165.3 (C=N), others signals : 103.7, 108.6, 129.8, 111.4, 162.5, 154.5, 122.6, 128.6, 128.6, 142.2, 128.6.

Crystallography :

Colourless block crystals of compound **1** suitable for an X-ray structure determination were obtained from

methanol by slow evaporation. All measurements were made at 293(2) K on Bruker Kappa Apex II-CCD diffractometer fitted with graphite-monochromated MoK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.7103 \text{ \AA}$) and corrected by multi scan method. The structure was solved by direct method using SIR92 and refinement of structure was done using SHELXL-97^{24–26}. Refinement of structure was carried out on F² using a full-matrix least square procedures. Crystallography data are given in Table 1 while molecular structure ORTEP diagram and packing structure diagram for compound **1** are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial activity was assessed by agar well diffusion method using 20 ml of sterile nutrient agar (Hi-Media) and potato-dextrose agar (Hi-Media) and sabouraud dextrose agar (Hi-Media) for testing the bacterial and filamentous fungal and yeast activity²⁷. The antifungal activities of the compounds were tested with *C. albicans* and *A. niger* and, for antibacterial activity, the compounds were screened against *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella paratyphi* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The test cultures were swabbed on the top of the solidified media and allowed to dry for 10 min. Sterile 6 mm diameter cork borer were pierced in the agar. Each compound was diluted in 3 mg/ml. The dilutions of the compounds concentration were deposited 20 μL on the inoculated well and left for 10 min at room temperature for the compound diffusion. Negative control was prepared using DMSO. Amphotericin-B (Hi-Media) for fungi and yeast; Ciprofloxacin (Hi-Media) for bacteria were served as positive control. The plates were inoculated with bacteria and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h and for fungal cultures,

incubated at 30 °C for 24–48 h. The experiment was repeated thrice and the average results were recorded. The antimicrobial activity was determined by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone (mm) around the well. The susceptibility of microbial was determined by minimum inhibitory concentration determination method²⁸. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of the compounds were determined by serial dilution against the micro-organisms. The minimum concentrations at which no visible growths were observed are defined as the MICs, which were expressed in µg/ml.

Conclusion

Sulphonamide compounds **1-4** were synthesized and characterized by IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral analysis and structure of compound **1** was determined by X-Ray crystallography. X-Ray structure analysis of the compound reveals the protonation of azomethine nitrogen atom with the formation of alkenyl *keto*-sulphonamide compound. All the compounds were screened for their antifungal and antibacterial activity and also determined their minimum inhibitory concentrations against various microbes. Compound **1** and **2** exhibit moderate activity against Gram +ve and -ve fungal species while **3** and **4** shown moderate activity against Gram +ve and -ve bacteria species. These compounds are less effective than the standard drugs.

Supplementary materials

Crystallographic data for structural analysis of compound **1** have been deposited with Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC No. 920603. Copy of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB21EZ, UK (Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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